

Identifying Teaching Patterns in Pre-service Informatics Teacher Education

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Abstract

This paper presents a case study of $N = 3$ seminars in teacher education in informatics, in which the overall goal is to identify and describe effective teaching patterns for easy reuse. Therefore, this case study first examines learning and instructional designs and their implications with ($N = 9$) pre-service informatics teachers and ($N = 3$) university teachers as instructional scenarios with associated evaluation data, and then uses them to identify best practices. It is argued in this poster that best examples of instructional settings in pre-service informatics teacher education can be assessed and finally reused. First results show insights in the impact of giving feedback in seminars. We conclude this poster with some implications for learning and instructional design in informatics.

Keywords

Teaching patterns, Taxonomy, Technology-enhanced learning and instruction

1. Introduction

When designing teaching for pre-service informatics teachers, the choice of digital tools and teaching methods needs to be aligned with the intended learning outcomes [1]. However, teachers design their lectures based on their epistemological assumptions on good teaching and learning [2]. In informatics in particular, the seminars need to address the acquisition of algorithmic and computational thinking. Computational thinking includes areas such as abstraction, decomposition, but is also the ability to design algorithms and interpret the world based on computer science knowledge [3, 4, 5, 6]. To assess instructional quality, several features of instructional quality have been identified and categorized as distinctive predictors of students' learning [7, 8]. Considering the pattern approach [9, 10, 11], it is aimed to identify teaching patterns. Hence, the following research question is driving this study: *To what extent can teaching examples in informatics be conceptualized, and teaching patterns be identified in teacher education?*

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2. Method

In order to identify the patterns, the collected data needs to be empirically analyzed. Therefore, data is structured according to computer science content, methodological approaches, and key characteristics of teaching quality. Considering this, to identify initial evidence for patterns, our research efforts are based on the case study approach as described by [12] in the mixed methods paradigm [13, 14] and are embedded in the design-based research approach [15] [16]. We quantitatively assess the instructional quality with an instrument which was already piloted and showed a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.95 [17]. Both, the teachers and the learners evaluated the instructional quality. Every item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = not at all true, 2 = rather not true, 3 = neither false nor true, 4 = rather true, 5 totally true). Moreover, the teachers were interviewed afterwards and were asked to fill out the evaluation survey regarding the digital tools that were used and additional information on their instructional setting into our databases. Three courses in informatics for teacher education were assessed: two courses on didactics and one course on database: **Didactics of Informatics**: students learn how to apply and integrate different didactic models when designing teaching sessions in informatics. **Seminar on Didactics**: Students run workshops with pupils and are videotaped. During the semester, they reflect their teaching competencies based on these video recordings. **Databases**: The course introduces the concept of relational database technology. Students work in groups to design and implement their own databases. N = 24 students in informatics participated in three different courses. However, not all of them filled out the evaluation surveys. The sample consists of N = 9 pre-service teachers in informatics. N = 3 in the didactics of informatics (1 female and 2 males with an average age of 24), N = 4 in the seminar on didactics (1 female and 3 males with an average age of 25), N = 2 in databases (2 males with an average age of 27).

3. Preliminary Results

We analyzed the mean scores (M) and the standard derivations (SD) of each workshop to examine the instructional quality. Table 1 illustrates a descriptive overview of the means and standard deviations for all scales. The course where most teachers participated by giving feedback to the students and prompted them through questions was rated very high in all scales. However, the course size was very small and not all students filled out the evaluation in the end.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this paper, we explored three different courses in informatics, which included feedback on students' performances from the teachers, and from the learners. The first assumption which emerges from these preliminary descriptive results is that, receiving feedback from multiple teachers' perspectives positively impacts the student's learning process. Moreover, it indicates that becoming teachers need to be trained on how to provide feedback to the learners on their learning outcomes. In future steps, this assumption needs to be investigated with larger samples by evaluating whether providing students with multiple feedback and by bringing them to reflect on their learning outcomes from multiple perspectives impacts their learning process.

Table 1
Description of the Instructional Quality

Scale	Didactics of Informatics N = 3		Seminar on Didactics N = 4		Databases N = 2	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Self-efficacy	3.67	0.58	3.75	1.50	4.50	0.71
Structuring	3.73	0.70	4.25	0.64	5.00	0.00
Activating	3.75	0.90	4.69	0.63	5.00	0.00
Motivating	4.17	0.29	4.63	0.60	4.50	0.35
Learning strategies	4.00	0.25	4.44	0.72	4.75	0.00
Feedback	4.00	1.00	4.00	0.41	4.25	0.35
Interest	3.92	0.58	4.17	1.44	5.00	0.00
Offer variants	4.67	0.00	3.75	0.96	5.00	0.00
Constructive alignment	4.67	0.00	4.33	0.47	4.67	0.00
Level of difficulty	4.00	0.00	4.75	0.71	4.00	0.00
Teacher	4.42	0.38	4.44	0.38	4.63	0.18
Total	3.82	0.43	4.32	0.73	4.73	0.09

At this stage, our case study is limited to various points that must be addressed in future stages. Data mining is normally based on a huge set of data [18]. A constraint of our case study is the limited amount of empirical data used to run the pattern processing. Once these limitations and future research aims have been addressed, structuring data in a database will offer new data mining approaches. The identification of best teaching practice patterns then can further result in innovative changes in teacher education in informatics aimed at easy reuse and transfer of informatics teaching best practices.

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